

Generalising XTRACT Tractography Protocols Across Common Macaque Brain Templates

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Introduction

Non-human primates are extensively used in neuroscience research as models of the human brain, with the rhesus macaque being a prominent example. We previously introduced a common space framework for probing brain differences across evolution and development, but also for identifying homologies in the human and macaque brain [1,2,3]. The common space is anchored on white matter (WM) landmarks. To map these landmarks, we previously devised tractography protocols (FSL's XTRACT) [2] that allow a set of 42 WM tracts to be correspondingly defined and reconstructed in the human and macaque brain (as well as the neonatal human [3]). Our original tractography protocols were developed using the F99 macaque brain template [4]. However, a diverse set of macaque brain templates have become available and are commonly used [5] (for instance NMT, Yerkes, INIA). Here, we generalise the XTRACT tractography protocol definitions across common macaque brain templates. We further explore whether the within-animal connectivity patterns, produced using protocols based on macaque templates other than F99, are highly correlated to those obtained using the standard F99 template.

Methods

Post-mortem ex-vivo dMRI brain data (7T Agilent DirectDrive, DW-SEMS, 0.6mm isotropic resolution, 16 b=0s/mm², 128 b=4000s/mm²) of 6 rhesus macaques were used [2,3]. Fibre orientation estimation for each dataset was performed using parametric spherical deconvolution (FSL's bedpostx) and orientation estimates were used for probabilistic tractography. 42 F99-space XTRACT protocols (Fig 1-B) [2,5] were transformed to 4 other macaque template spaces using the RheMAP pipeline [5], which is based on ANTs non-linear registration (Fig 1C). These templates were based on both in-vivo and ex-vivo anatomical (T1w) MRI data and included: D99 [7], INIA19 [8], NMTv2.0 [9], Yerkes19 (YRK) [10] (Fig 1D). ANTs non-linear warp fields were converted to FSL format and used with XTRACT. Protocols in the new template spaces were manually refined where registration caused imperfections (for instance in cases of CBP, CST and AC). Subject-wise non-linear transformations to each of the 5 template spaces were obtained using FSL's FNIRT, based on subject FA maps. Subsequently, XTRACT reconstructed 42 native-space tracts for each animal, based on protocols defined in each template space (Fig 1C). Per WM tract, the correlation between the native-space path distribution obtained using protocols from the 4 new templates and F99 was calculated, per subject, and summarised as the median +/- MAD across subjects.

Results

WM tracts were reconstructed for each subject using each template protocol (Fig 2A). Qualitatively, we observed high agreement between the connectivity patterns generated using the standard F99 and each other template (Fig 2A) protocol across subjects. Quantitatively, for the majority of the 42 WM tracts, median correlation was greater than 0.9 between F99 and every other template across subjects (Fig 2B). For each tract category (association, commissural, limbic, projection), the median agreement between the F99 and the in-vivo templates was ~0.99, as well as for the ex-vivo templates. These results support the robustness of our pipeline to template variability, allowing its reliable use with other commonly employed templates of the macaque brain.

Conclusion

We presented generalised XTRACT tractography protocols that are robust across different commonly used macaque brain template spaces. As they are also correspondingly defined for the human brain, they allow greater flexibility and integration of our WM-based common space framework for probing brain differences and similarities across evolution and development.

References

1. Mars, R.B. et al. 2018. "Whole Brain Comparative Anatomy Using Connectivity Blueprints." *eLife* 7(e35237).
2. Warrington, S. et al. 2020. "XTRACT - Standardised Protocols for Automated Tractography in the Human and Macaque Brain." *NeuroImage*. 217: 116923
3. Warrington, S. et al. 2022. "Concurrent mapping of brain ontogeny and phylogeny within a common space: Standardized tractography and applications." *Sci. Adv.* 8, eabq2022.
4. Folloni D. et al. 2019. "Dichotomous organization of amygdala/temporal-prefrontal bundles in both humans and monkeys." *eLife* 2019;8:e47175. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.47175>
5. Van Essen, DC. Et al. 2002a. "Surface-based atlases of cerebellar cortex in the human, macaque, and mouse." *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 978:468--479.
6. Sirmipilatzte N. et al. 2020. "RheMAP: Non-linear warps between common rhesus macaque brain templates." *Neuroimage*. 117519.
7. Reveley C., et al. 2017. "Three-Dimensional Digital Template Atlas of the Macaque Brain". *Cerebral Cortex*. 27: 4463–4477.
8. Rohlfing T. et al. 2012. "The INIA19 template and NeuroMaps atlas for primate brain image parcellation and spatial normalization." *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*. 6(1):27.
9. Seidlitz J. et al. 2018. "A population MRI brain template and analysis tools for the macaque." *Neuroimage*. 170:121-131.
10. Donahue C.J. et al. 2016. "Using Diffusion Tractography to Predict Cortical Connection Strength and Distance: A Quantitative Comparison with Tracers in the Monkey." *The Journal of Neuroscience*. 36(25):6758-6770.

*All templates were resampled to isotropic 0.50mm resolution (where necessary).

Figure 1: (A) Tract atlases from the adult human and macaque brain. (B) WM tracts protocols used in XTRACT. (C) Protocols are transformed from standard F99 space to each other template space of choice using nonlinear registration. For each subject, XTRACT with each of the protocols gives WM tract estimates in subject space, allowing for comparison between templates. (D) All Macaque templates considered including the standard (F99).

Figure 2: XTRACT results from 6 Macaque subjects using 5 different templates. (A) Resulting WM tracts from XTRACT using each of the templates: F99, D99-SL, INIA19, NMT, YRK. Qualitative comparison between templates for all major WM tracts considered. (B) Median correlation across subjects for each tract between F99 and each other template was used for template comparison and assessment of XTRACT generalizability. Median \pm MAD of correlation value between F99 and each of the other templates considered for each WM tract across 6 subjects. Correlation was calculated per subject and per tract between F99 and each other template. The median \pm MAD was calculated per tract across subjects for each template comparison. Median correlation was greater than 0.9 across all WM tracts and templates supporting the robustness and generalizability of XTRACT across Macaque templates.